

CURE MONITORING OF 3D ANGLE INTERLOCK WOVEN CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES

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1 Abstract

This study presents a methodology to accurately embed fibre optic sensors within the resin channels of 3D woven composite for the purpose of monitoring strain during the cure cycle/resin infusion of a 3D woven composite.

The cure induced strain measurement was developed into a valid in situ cure monitoring technique for an epoxy matrix 3D composite through correlation with rheological based cure strain data and conventional thermal analysis cure monitoring techniques. Specific strain events were attributed to the gelation and vitrification phases of the epoxy cure cycle.

2 Introduction

Woven composites materials are susceptible to transverse impact loading which causes laminas to become delaminated [1]. Various methods have been developed to improve the impact tolerance including z-pinning, selective interlayers and hybrids, protective layers or resin toughening; one method that is becoming increasingly successful is to reinforce composites with a fibre that connects the layers together running from the upper to lower surface of the laminate. Mouritz et al. [2] stated that 3D woven composites have higher ballistic damage resistance and impact tolerance than 2D materials, higher tensile strain and strain-to-failure values, and also higher interlaminar fracture toughness; this might be beneficial in the design of primary aircraft structures where the limiting design criteria is compression after impact [3,4]. Furthermore, 3D woven textile reinforced composites allow the optimisation and tailoring of specific material properties into the final component that can provide a reduction in manufacturing cost [5]. However, earlier research measuring the tensile strength and modulus in both the warp and weft direction [6]

showed that where the binder travels through the thickness of the fabric a resin rich area is created. A fibre optic sensing system was selected as it has been shown that they can be successfully embedded within the carbon fibre reinforced composite (CFRP) structure without causing degradation in the performance of the material [7, 8]. They have been successfully employed in this strain sensing role within CFRP materials in several studies to measure fatigue strains [9], impact damage [10, 11] delamination [12], flexural strains [13] and tensile strains [14]. Oliveira et al [15] outline that EFPI sensors offer a greater level of sensitivity to strain measurement when compared to other fibre optic strain sensing systems such as Bragg grating sensors (Figure 1). Leng [16] and Liu [17] both outline that EFPI strain sensors are insensitive to temperature change. Angle Interlock 3D woven composites have previously been shown to provide manufacturing advantages, yet also provide a structure where the advantages of low crimp tows bound together by a binder tow, result in a composite with high performance and reduced sensitivity to interlaminar shear [18]. This paper investigates the in situ cure monitoring technique for an epoxy matrix using the same sensors. Several works have been able to monitor cure progression by measuring the change in dimension of an epoxy/thermosetting polymer attributing changes in cure shrinkage development to the phase transformations of gelation and vitrification [19, 20, 21, 22]. However these techniques are adaptations of laboratory based techniques and therefore cannot be directly applied to use in the composite manufacturing environment. Epoxy resin contracts as cure progresses as a consequence of chemically induced volumetric shrinkage due to cross-linking [23, 24]. Fibre optic sensors have been able to record the changes in internal strain of CFRP during the curing of the

epoxy resin and therefore used this as a measure of cure progression [25].

3 Methodology

The loom used was a DATAWEAVE loom with Jacquard controller incorporating 1152 hooks. A specific weave architecture that consist of long continuous lengths of tows for maximum strength in the 0/90° directions and have angle interlock binding configurations in-order to suppress delaminations was manufactured (Figure 2). The details regarding the weave architecture of them has been reported previously by Buchanan et al. [16] EFPI sensors were embedded between layer 1 and 2, and layers 3 and 4 of the 4 warp layer fabric. This arrangement was selected as these positions would be expected to have a significant difference in V_f and therefore tensile performance. Fabrics with embedded EFPI sensors were infused with polymer and processed into composites via a modified VaRTM technique. Fabrics were infused with the 2 part epoxy resin system of Huntsman Araldite® LY-564 resin and Aradur® HY-2954 hardener. The processed 3D woven carbon fibre reinforced plastic (3DWCFRP) for this investigation had a V_f 58.67% +/- 1.3% which is comparable to similar materials produced through works by Archer [6] and Buchanan [18].

A TA Instruments AR2000 rheometer was used to carry out initial measurements of chemically induced volumetric shrinkage and thus providing a reliable baseline of cure shrinkage measurements for future comparison with Extrinsic Fabry Perot Interferometer (EFPI) cure shrinkage measurements. The instrument was set up in parallel plate configuration with 25mm diameter aluminium plates. Baseline experiments were carried out at 60°C, 80°C, and 100°C isothermal cure temperatures. Strain was controlled to 1%. A low strain value was selected as Winter showed that high strains could cause shear thinning and therefore prolonged gel times [26]. 1% strain also allowed the experiments to carry on beyond vitrification i.e. when the epoxy had solidified. Measurement frequency was restricted to 1Hz. as this would provide consistent gelation measurement at the $G'-G''$ crossover.

To measure shrinkage the "normal force control" function was utilised on the TA AR2000. The

AR2000 was therefore set to maintain a constant compressive force on the sample. To provide the baseline EFPI cure shrinkage measurement, the AR2000 rheometer was used purely as a furnace to provide accurate temperature control, capable of temperature ramps and isothermal hold. The design of the AR2000 furnace allowed for the safe passage of the optical fibre lead from the sensor head to the interrogation unit, as the sensor lead could be routed up and out the drive shaft orifice. This meant that the furnace seal was not interfered with and the driveshaft was unobstructed. The AR2000 was programmed to replicate the heating cycles used in the earlier experiments i.e. ramp, from ambient temperature, at 10°C/min and then hold at the selected isothermal cure temperature for 5 hours. During the cycle the FiberPro 2 system continuously monitored the strain from within the curing epoxy. The FiberPro 2 scans the strain response at 960Hz with a sampling rate of 1/1000. During the resin injection and subsequent curing the EFPI sensors were continuously logging strain measurements during the cure cycle. This cure cycle would also be programmed in to the experiments using the modified rheological technique for direct comparison with the cure induced strain data collected from the EFPI sensors during the resin infusion process.

4 Results

When comparing the loom state fabric (Figure 3) to the VaRTM manufactured composite (Figure 4) for the Angle interlock fabric the main difference appears to be the change in tow cross sectional shape in both the warp and weft direction. Figure 5 shows the 4 warp layers and changing resin rich regions caused by the binder displacing warp yarns in an angle-interlock composite. Figure 6 shows that the EFPI sensor between layers 1 and 2 is embedded within the resin channel at this level and is in an area of localised low fibre volume fraction. Whereas, conversely, Figure 7 shows that the EFPI sensor between layers 3 and 4 has been embedded in the resin channel but it is surrounded by both its adjacent warp tow and the binder and is therefore in an area of localised high fibre volume fraction. Figures 8 & 9 are micrographs, illustrating the levels at which the EFPI sensors have been embedded within the composite.

Cure induced strain was recorded by means of a modified rheological experiment, wherein control of the normal/axial force exerted on the curing polymer only sample was controlled, enabling the change in dimension of the curing sample or change in gap distance between the parallel plates of the rheometer to be monitored. Figure 10 shows the typical strain response from the curing epoxy measured via the rheological technique during isothermal curing at 60, 80, and 100°C with initial ramps rates of 10°C/min to each cure temperature.

From the traces presented in Figure 10, for all temperatures, it is evident that strain evolution during the cure of this epoxy resin system undergoes five distinct phases, those being:

1. Initial strain drop
2. Equilibrium
3. Trough/sudden strain drop
4. Strain increase to peak
5. Exponential decrease in strain after peak

From the known cure behaviour of epoxy resin systems, phase one and two can be attributed to the heating ramp phase, and the subsequent isothermal hold at the chosen cure temperature causing the initial decrease in viscosity allowing for the resin to flow and therefore decrease in dimension. This then equalized once the resin reached the isothermal cure temperature. It should be noted at this stage that an increase in strain is considered expansion and a decrease in strain is considered as shrinkage. Phase three is Gelation which was defined as the first development of strain after the equilibrium period (Phase 2). At 80°C and 100°C this was manifested in a slight decrease in strain transcending into Phase 4. Through the comparison of this event to the data collected from the rheological experiments, Phase 3 could be attributed to the gelation process of this particular epoxy resin system (LY 564/HY 2954). Phase 4 shows an apparent increase in strain. Phase 5 is Vitrification defined as being the point at which strain levels begin to decrease or the onset of a higher rate of strain reduction/shrinkage. This can be attributed to the now glassy properties of the curing epoxy i.e. the epoxy is now a solid and can no longer exhibit the viscous flow of a gel or the Newtonian properties of its liquid state. Therefore any force

imparted within the epoxy by further cross-linking reactions, will result in a reduction in volume as the Van der Waals attractions between polymer chains get substituted for shorter covalent bonds, effectively pulling the newly formed epoxy macromolecule closer together. Vitrification is a process and the beginning of this process coincides with the onset of strain reduction/shrinkage. This point has been defined as vitrification as from a composite processing point of view this point indicates the physical gel - solid transformation. Shrinkage/strain reduction continues monotonically because the cure process is ongoing, causing further vitrification until the glass transition temperature of the epoxy reaches the cure temperature, at which point the cure will slow to zero and will not continue unless further energy is input to the system i.e. the cure temperature is raised.

Now that a reliable baseline of how cure induced strain develops in the unreinforced epoxy resin, LY 564/HY 2954, has been obtained and that accurate measurements of gelation and vitrification have been extrapolated from events in the strain data, it is now applicable to move forward and investigate the ability of the EFPI sensing system to monitor cure induced strain whilst embedded within the LY 564/HY 2954 resin system. Experiments were carried out, that repeated the cure cycles utilised in the above-mentioned work, on samples of the LY 564/HY 2954 resin system with embedded EFPI fibre optic strain sensors. The use of the controlled environment of the AR2000 furnace, to conduct the EFPI experiments, allowed for accurate temperature control and therefore the collection of directly comparable data to that obtained from the rheological cure strain measuring technique. Figure 11 displays the strain plots obtained from these experiments. Each strain plot measured during each of the respective isothermal cure cycles exhibits a similar response to that measured from the rheological strain experiments. Once again there are two specific points of interest on each plot. After an initial softening phase during which strain drops to an equilibrium as the isothermal cure temperature is reached, the strain plot undergoes a point of inflexion and then continues to a point at which the strain levels begin to decrease at a higher rate monotonically.

The development and evolution of strain measured by the EFPI sensors, produces plots of strain versus time that are similar/resemble, to a high degree, cure strain plots presented by both Harsch et al and Leng et al [25, 26,] measured by both EFPI and Bragg grating fibre optic strain measuring techniques, embedded in an unreinforced epoxy resin system and pre-impregnated carbon fibre respectively. The results are summarised in Table 1.

Finally data was recorded from the resin infusion process of 3DWCFRP with embedded EFPI sensors. For comparison with the strain data recorded from the embedded EFPI sensors, the modified rheological experiment is once again utilised and in this instance it is programmed to simulate the VARTM heating cycle. That being, injection at 75°C; once injection/full wet out is complete the temperature is ramped at 0.48C/min to 100°C; isothermal hold at 100°C for 1 hour. Figure 12 displays representative plots of the strain data collected from the EFPI sensors within the curing 3DCFRP matrix and the rheological VARTM cure cycle simulation.

The rheological strain plot displayed in Figure 12 is consistent with the rheological strain data collected previously from this technique even though in this instance a complex cure cycle has been simulated i.e. the slow ramp rate to the isothermal cure temperature. In this case the equilibrium phase is not present as the continuous temperature ramp results in the decreasing viscosity allowing for a longer softening phase. However the end of this phase is marked with the synonymous inflection/trough indicating gelation. As in the isothermal experiments the strain level rises to the peak indicating vitrification. The strain rise being attributed once again to the overcompensation of the normal force control, due to the normal force induced as a result of gelation exceeding the normal force tolerance set in the experiment program. After vitrification, strain decreases in a similar manner to that displayed by the isothermal experiments. The EFPI strain plot displayed in Figure 12 mimics closely the rheological response discussed above. Table 2 summarises the conclusions drawn above by displaying a direct comparison of the believed gelation and vitrification measurements extrapolated from the each strain monitoring technique.

Table 2 shows that the measurements of gelation and vitrification, extrapolated from each of the measurement techniques, displays a low standard deviation and variation. This allows for a high degree of confidence in the data presented. However, through the comparison of the gelation and vitrification times it is evident that there is a significant difference between the times recorded by each technique. In fact there is 10% difference in the gelation measurement and an 18% difference in the values for vitrification times. There is a simple explanation for this difference between the two measurement techniques, that being that the rheological experiment does not account for the 5 minute injection time that occurs at the start of the VARTM process, the end of which is indicated by the beginning of the strain equilibrium phase illustrated in Figure 12. When the 5 minute injection time is taken into account, the difference in the gelation and vitrification measurements falls to 3.5% and 5.7% respectively. Which is acceptable considering this is the comparison of a highly controlled, laboratory based, experimental technique to an industrial manufacturing process.

5 Conclusions

EFPI fibre optic system has the ability to monitor cure of epoxy resin systems in a laboratory environment but more importantly, for this project and the advancement of 3DWCFRP, in the industrial manufacturing process as this shows potential for direct industrial application and the further application of 3DWCFRP in mainstream industry.

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7 References

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Fig. 1. Schematic of EFPI sensor head.

Fig. 2. Representation of the weave architecture.

Fig. 3. Longitudinal (a) and transverse (b) micrograph of Angle interlock loom state composite.

Fig. 4. Longitudinal (a) and transverse (b) micrograph of angle interlock composite.

Fig. 5. Micrograph taken in the warp direction showing the changing resin rich regions caused by the binder displacing warp yarns in an angle-interlock 3DWCFRP.

Fig. 6. Micrograph taken in the weft direction showing EFPI sensor embedded in the resin channel in warp layer

Fig. 7. Micrograph taken in the weft direction showing EFPI sensor embedded in the resin channel in warp layer 3.

Fig. 8. Micrograph cut along warp direction showing EFPI sensor embedded in the resin channel in warp layer 2.

Fig 9. Micrograph cut along warp direction showing EFPI sensor embedded in the resin channel in warp layer 3.

CURE TEMP (°C)	RHEOMETER		
	MEAN	STAND DEVIATION	COEFFICIENT OF VARIATION
60	124.71	1.67	1.34
80	44.96	2.17	4.82
100	21.74	0.61	2.84

Table 1. Summary of gel times measured by rheometry.

Fig. 11. Baseline EFPI cure induced strain measurement.

Fig. 10. Representative plot of cure induced strain evolution with time.

Fig. 12. Real time cure induced strain data measured from an embedded EFPI sensor within a 3D woven composite during resin infusion compared to cure induced strain measured from cure cycle simulation via the modified rheological technique.

	TIME TO GELATION (MIN)			TIME TO VITRIFICATION (MIN)		
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variation	Mean	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variation
RHEOLOGICAL STRAIN	33.86	0.92	2.71	73.115	3.55	4.86
EFPI STRAIN	37.54	2.05	5.48	82.86	3.49	4.21

Table 2. Comparison of both cure induced strain measurement techniques.